

Setting behaviour and bioactivity assessment of calcium carbonate cements

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Setting behaviour and bioactivity assessment of calcium carbonate cements

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Abstract

Calcium carbonate cements have emerged in the last few years as an attractive candidate for biomedical applications. They can be easily prepared by mixing water with two metastable calcium carbonate phases - amorphous calcium carbonate (ACC) and vaterite-, which (re)crystallize into calcite during setting reaction. The transformation kinetics (and therefore the final cement composition) strongly depends on the initial mixture design and is controlled by the dissolution of ACC, whereas calcite nucleation typically controls their recrystallization in fluid batch experiments. Novel compositions are presented in this paper by incorporating organic molecules as a proxy to test their capability to carry on other biomolecules like proteins or antibiotics. The hardened samples are microporous and show excellent bioactivity rates, although their mechanical properties still remain poor. However, this would not be a handicap for in-vivo applications such as bone filling, especially in low mechanical stress locations.

Keywords: CaCO₃ cements, (re)crystallization kinetics, bioactivity, apatite-like precipitation, compressive strength.

1. Introduction

Biomedical ceramics and cements were the first synthetic approaches employed by orthopedics and surgeons to overcome the inherent difficulties associated with natural bone-substitute materials (viral and/or bacterial contamination risks, biological variability or difficulty of supply). More specifically, calcium phosphate cements (CPCs) were the most used and attractive alternatives as a result of their excellent biocompatibility and bioactive properties (1,2). However, the limited solubility of their main constituent phase (apatite) still represents their leading drawback and in consequence, several CPCs containing more soluble mineral compounds (like calcium sulfate or calcium carbonate, for example (3–5)) were developed to improve their biological resorption rate and subsequent bone formation. Some authors went beyond that idea and proposed cement compositions entirely made of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) (6–8), opening new possibilities since they exhibit not only higher solubility but larger porosity and faster resorption rates among many other advantages.

CaCO_3 is a simple compound and one of the most abundant minerals throughout nature. Listed from the most to the least thermodynamically stable, it exists in three different anhydrous crystalline phases (calcite, aragonite and vaterite), two hydrated phases (ikaite and monohydrocalcite) and one amorphous calcium carbonate (ACC) phase. The feasibility of sintering cements entirely made of CaCO_3 from those phases was already demonstrated by *Combes et al.* (9). The authors stated that it is necessary to prepare biphasic mixtures of calcium carbonate powders comprising metastable phases. More specifically, one of those should be the highly reactive ACC phase while the other should be one of the metastable crystalline phases, i.e. either vaterite or aragonite, to serve as seeds and orient the (re)crystallization of the mixture into a more stable calcium carbonate crystalline phase in the presence of small amounts of water. Nevertheless, a better understanding of this (re)crystallization process is still necessary to optimize these materials since the adequate tuning of the cement composition is crucial to achieve a satisfactory clinical use.

Cements, unlike sintered and natural materials can be easily associated with active biological molecules like proteins or antibiotics (10,11). However, there is still a lack of understanding about the interactions between

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3 organic materials and inorganic cements. For instance, polysaccharides, fatty acids (olive oil) and Nopal juice (a
4 plant extract) have been used in traditional lime mortars to improve some of their properties (12) but in most
5 cases they displayed a negligible impact on the mechanical strength (13). Nevertheless, recent research has
6 shown that the presence of organic molecules in chalk (a carbonate sedimentary rock) is key to understand it's
7 strength on geological time scales (14). Chalk consists of tiny calcium carbonate crystals (in the form of calcite)
8 that are intrinsically very reactive. If these crystals could recrystallize, chalk would have a very high creep rate
9 under its own load. However, the recrystallization is passivated by the presence of organic molecules. Thus,
10 when a crack appears, the crack surfaces consist of fresh unpassivated calcite that can react to heal the crack.
11 Consequently, the presence of organic additives within cement microstructures may open new possibilities in
12 terms of enhanced mechanical properties and endowment of self-healing properties that will be of great interest,
13 especially for biomedical applications.
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16 In the present study we evaluate the reaction kinetics and the composition during setting and hardening of
17 calcium carbonate cements, both in the absence and incorporating octanoic acid as a proxy to test their
18 capability to carry on biomolecules like proteins or antibiotics and/or to endow them with self-healing
19 properties. Moreover, we assess their bone bioactivity by checking the ability of apatite-like compounds to form
20 on their surface after immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF) as a common practice in the field of bioactive
21 materials (15–17). The study covers several immersion periods after which both their mechanical properties and
22 degree of apatite precipitation are evaluated.
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25 26 **2. Materials and methods**

27 28 *2.1. Preparation of CaCO₃ powders*

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30 The preparation of CaCO₃ cements requires the synthesis of different calcium carbonate polymorphs in order to
31 design the initial cement mixture (9). Accordingly, both ACC and vaterite phases were prepared as described on
32 (18). Briefly, they were precipitated by mixing calcium chloride (CaCl₂·6H₂O, Sigma Aldrich) and sodium
33 carbonate (Na₂CO₃, Sigma Aldrich) equimolar (0.5 M) solutions, prepared with ultrapure Milli-Q water (18.2
34 MΩ cm), at room temperature using a magnetic stirrer set at 400 rpm. Following *Ogino et al.* (19) we used
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3 reaction time 10 sec for ACC and 30 min for vaterite. To wash off any dissolved sodium chloride (NaCl), the
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5 CaCO_3 precipitates were rinsed with deionized water and ethanol, using a filtering kit and 0.5 μm pore-size filter
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7 papers (Millipore, USA). Subsequently, the CaCO_3 precipitates were flushed with liquid N_2 to stop the
8
9 recrystallization of these metastable phases. The frozen precipitates were lyophilized (Alpha 1-4 LD plus,
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11 Martin Christ, Germany) for 48 h at 0.05 mbars and -50°C and stored in a freezer (-22°C) with additional silica
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13 powder bags to keep them as dry as possible (20) prior to cement manufacturing.

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16 The precipitates were scanned by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Bruker D8 Discover X-ray diffractometer) to
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18 identify the crystalline phases present using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation (30 mA and 40 kV) and recording 2θ angles from
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20 20 to 50° at a 0.04 s^{-1} sweep rate. Additionally, they were imaged with scanning electron microscopy (SEM)
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22 (Hitachi SU5000 Field-Emission; 1kV acceleration voltage and 3.0 mm working distance).

23 24 25 2.2. Preparation of CaCO_3 cements

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28 Following the method outlined by *Combes et al.* (9), we synthesized CaCO_3 cements with different
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30 microstructures by mixing ACC and vaterite powders in different weight ratios (wt.%): 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3,
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32 respectively, while keeping the liquid to solid ratio (L/S) constant (0.5). Vaterite was selected as our crystalline
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34 seed rather than aragonite to simplify the manufacture.

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37 To investigate the influence of organic molecules absorbing on the mineral surfaces within the cement
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39 microstructure, we have chosen to study a simple carboxylic acid: octanoic acid. Octanoic acid is a low soluble,
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41 eight-carbon saturated fatty acid, which can be found naturally in the milk of various mammals (21). Due to its
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43 length, it has been used as a cross-linker agent in several industries, including coatings and pharmaceuticals
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45 (22,23), and consequently it is an interesting candidate to provide self-healing properties to cement pastes. The
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47 carboxyl group of octanoic acid is known to absorb on calcite surfaces as monolayers (24) and can either inhibit
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49 further calcite growth or enhance it by templating. Two different concentrations, 0.4 and 0.8 v.%, of octanoic
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51 acid (OA) (Sigma-Aldrich) were added to the water phase prior to mixing with the solid phase. These values
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53 were chosen based on preliminary tests to find the maximum concentration of OA that allows setting of CaCO_3
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55 cement pastes ($C_{\text{max}} = 1.0\text{ v.}\%$).

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3 The notation used hereafter to refer to each composition is the following: 1:1 wt.%, 1:2 wt.% and 1:3 wt.% for
4 the pure compositions, and 1:2 wt.%+0.4 v% OA and 1:2 wt.%+0.8 v% OA for those containing organic
5 molecules. Just after mixing the powders with the liquid phase, the resulting pastes were viscous and easily
6 moldable for several minutes. Depending on the subsequent analysis, the pastes were placed either in sample
7 holders (to assess the reaction kinetics) or in specially designed oedometric presses (to assess their bioactivity
8 and strength evolution) (25). To ensure reproducibility, sufficient cement quantities were made to perform all
9 analyses on the same sample batch.
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18 *2.3. In-situ time-lapse XRD analysis of cement setting*

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21 To quantify the phase transformation kinetics during the setting reaction we have used *in-situ* x-ray diffraction
22 (XRD) at high temporal resolution (< 25 seconds) on the cement pastes. The fresh pastes were molded into
23 sample holders (25 mm discs, 2 mm depth) and firmly tamped immediately after mixing with water.
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28 To identify the crystalline phases present within the precipitates as a function of time, the CaCO₃ cement pastes
29 were scanned using a Bruker D8 A25 X-ray diffractometer with Mo K α radiation (48 mA and 48 kV) and
30 recording 2θ angles from 10 to 17° at a sweep rate of 0.035 s⁻¹ (See Supplementary Material, SM.1, for further
31 details). The reactions were considered complete when no further changes within the diffraction peak intensities
32 were observed. Further scans were launched after 28 days to discard any possible evolution of the
33 (re)crystallization process with time.
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41 *2.4. Bioactivity assessment in simulated body fluid*

42 *2.4.1. Sample preparation*

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45 For the *in-vitro* studies and accompanying strength testing, wet cement pastes (prepared as described on Section
46 2.2) were placed in specially designed oedometric presses (hollow cylinders, 12.0 cm in height and 2.0 cm inner
47 diameter) in between two porous, plastic-made, auxiliary discs (25). The inner walls of the presses were coated
48 with Teflon ®. A steel spring loaded uniaxially the assembly at about ~0.15 MPa. Thereupon, the presses were
49 placed inside an oven at physiological temperature (37 °C) for setting and hardening for the first 24 h. After that,
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3 the specimens were unmolded and left inside the oven for final drying. This process was followed by means of
4 their weight evolution using digital scales (Sartorius Lab Instruments, Germany, accuracy = 0.1 mg). After 7
5 days the weight of the samples reached a plateau value and they were cut into smaller cylinders using a metallic
6 saw and polishing paper (silicon carbide P80D) brought to 1.00 ± 0.02 cm in height and 0.50 ± 0.02 cm in
7 diameter. The final dimensions of the specimens were measured using a caliper and used to determine their
8 apparent density, ρ_a .
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16 2.4.2. *In-vitro* study with simulated body fluid

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18 Following Kokubo *et al.* (15), an acellular solution with an ionic composition similar to that of human plasma,
19 known as simulated body fluid (SBF), was prepared for the *in-vitro* study by dissolving the amounts of reagent
20 chemicals into distilled water (in order): NaCl (1.374 mM), NaHCO₃ (4.225 mM), KCl (3.018 mM),
21 K₂HPO₄·3H₂O (1.012 mM), MgCl₂·6H₂O (1.529 mM), CaCl₂·2H₂O (2.631 mM), and Na₂SO₄ (0.506 mM). The
22 next reagent was only added after the previous one was completely dissolved. Then, the solution pH was
23 adjusted to the physiological value (7.40) by HCl (1.0 M) addition and buffered by tris(hydroxyl-methyl)
24 aminomethane (50.505 mM).
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34 The small pressed cement cylinders were placed in polyethylene flasks, immersed in 50 mL of SBF and
35 incubated at constant temperature (37 °C) and orbital shaking (90 rpm) for different periods of time (1, 3, 7, 14
36 and 28 days). The SBF solution was refreshed every three days. After each immersion period, the pH of the
37 solution was measured and the specimens were rinsed; first with distilled water and then with ethanol to
38 terminate further reactions, followed by a 24 h drying period under a fume hood. Samples were stored in
39 desiccators until further examination.
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46 The formation of apatite-like crystals on the cements placed in the SBF flask was studied by several analytical
47 techniques. First, the dried solid samples were fixed on a support plate using silver paste in between, and
48 analyzed using a secondary electron microscope (1kV acceleration voltage and 3.0 mm working distance).
49 Second, scratched powder taken with a spatula from the outermost surface was analyzed with XRD and Fourier
50 transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). XRD patterns were collected using Cu K α radiation (30 mA and 40
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3 kV), recording 2θ angles from 20 to 50° at a sweep rate of 0.04 s⁻¹ and combined with the software Diffrac.EVA
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5 (Bruker AXS, USA) for crystalline phase identification. FTIR spectra were recorded using an attenuated total
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7 reflection (ATR) cell, in the transmittance mode and within the wavenumber interval 400-4000 cm⁻¹. The
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9 analysis was performed in triplicate over newly synthesized samples.
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11 12 *2.4.3 Compressive strength*

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14 The compressive strength of the cement cylinders used for the *in-vitro* bioactivity assessment was tested before
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16 and after each immersion period using a DEBEN CT5000 (UK) tensile/compression stage (5000 N load cell,
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18 0.01 N resolution), at a crosshead speed of 0.2 mm/min, corresponding to strain rates of 10⁻³ s⁻¹. From the
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20 recorded data (applied force and sample elongation), a stress-strain curve was constructed for each test. The
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22 uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) was computed on the basics of the maximum force applied at failure and
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24 the nominal cross-sectional area of each specimen using a in-house developed scrip in Matlab® (25). Three
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26 samples of each composition were tested to ensure repeatability.
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30 **3. Results and discussion**

31 32 *3.1. Characterization of the starting materials*

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34 As shown in (18), ACC precipitates (Figure 1A) consist of equidimensional spherical nanoparticles (<50 nm in
35
36 diameter) accompanied by rhombohedral crystals of about 50-100 nm. These are interpreted to be calcite and
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38 confirmed by XRD analysis (Figure 1C). Vaterite precipitates (Figure 1B) consist of spherical grains of 4-5 μm
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40 in diameter also accompanied by rhombohedral grains (4-5 μm), which are calcite according to the XRD scans
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42 (Figure 1C). Therefore, both ACC and vaterite precipitates are about 90% pure (from XRD analysis) with only
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44 minor amounts of calcite.
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Figure 1. Precipitated calcium carbonate powders in the form of (A) ACC phase and (B) Vaterite phase. (C) XRD patterns of (A) and (B) powders. (D) 3D plot of time-lapse XRD patterns obtained from the cement composition 1:1 wt% showing the evolution of the solid phases ACC, vaterite and calcite. Coloured peaks just to guide the eye.

3.2. (Re)crystallization analysis and final composition of CaCO_3 cements

Cement compositions and transformation kinetics of different CaCO_3 phases involved during setting and hardening processes are investigated by *in-situ* time-resolved XRD. Figure 1D includes an example 3D plot of the XRD patterns obtained from the cement composition 1:1 wt.%. At the base of each pattern there is a slightly curved baseline, resulting from the combined scattering of the poorly-ordered ACC and the aqueous solution (26). Moreover, immediately upon mixing of the starting reagents with water, the distinctive diffraction peaks of both vaterite and calcite are observed, with a more prominent calcite peak.

With ongoing transformation, the broad hump and the tandem vaterite peaks start to break down, while the calcite peaks become more prominent. It is important to highlight that the rates at which these phases dissolve and/or (re)crystallize do not only vary with time but also are concentration-dependent, so their values are different for each of the studied cement compositions.

3.2.1 The effect of starting composition

Figure 2 includes the calculated molar fractions, X_i , of the three calcium carbonate polymorphs (ACC, vaterite and calcite) that coexist during the setting reaction for three different CaCO_3 pure compositions (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.% ACC:V). It shows visually how the two starting phases – ACC and vaterite – are dissolving while the third one – calcite – is growing at the expense of the other two. The results show that the reaction rate, and thus the crystallization process, depends on the initial weight ratio between ACC and vaterite powders, as does the total duration of reaction. Moreover, it seems that only the 1:1 wt.% paste is able to complete the transformation. After 10 hours of reaction, the remaining amount of vaterite for this composition is almost undetectable ($2 \pm 1\%$) and the specimen is entirely made of calcite ($98 \pm 2\%$). Thus, both setting and hardening processes are fast enough to complete the (re)crystallization of the initial admixture into the most stable CaCO_3 phase before drying.

The 1:2 wt.% paste transforms more rapidly than the previous composition, following a linear evolution up to 3 hours of reaction when it starts to deviate. After ~ 4.5 hours no more changes among crystalline diffraction intensities are detected and the reaction is stopped. Nevertheless, the results show that the drying process does not allow a complete transformation of the initial phases since the set sample contains $66 \pm 2\%$ calcite and $33 \pm 1\%$ untransformed vaterite.

An even faster crystallization mechanism, as well as earlier termination, can be recognized for the 1:3 wt.% composition. Calcite transformation kinetics also follows a linear evolution and after 3 hours of reaction, a sudden arrest makes the set sample to be composed by $59 \pm 2\%$ calcite and $40 \pm 1\%$ untransformed vaterite. The complete arrest of transformation of vaterite into calcite coincides in time with the completion of transformation of ACC. The coupling of the transformation kinetic timescales of vaterite and ACC in these experiments is in contrast to the decoupled timescales of transformation in previous experiments, where the samples were plastic covered to avoid evaporation (18). However, during the experiments here presented there was water evaporation to allow a more natural coupling of setting and drying. The fact that when there is no more ACC all transformation stops suggests that water is mainly trapped in the very small pores between the tiny ACC grains,

whereas the coarser vaterite grains dry out quickly and are only supplied with water for transformation by the adjacent ACC. All these results are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2. Calcite, vaterite and ACC mole fractions, X_i , evolution with time for three different pure CaCO_3 cement compositions (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 wt.% ACC:V), and two CaCO_3 cement compositions containing organics. Solid symbols represent calcite while empty symbols and dashed lines stand for vaterite and ACC, respectively.

In order to model this behaviour, we follow (18) and describe the crystal dissolution rate, r (See SM. 2, for further details).

Previously (18), we found that for wet CaCO_3 cements the transformation mechanism was limited by the dissolution of vaterite and not by the available surface area of calcite as has been reported for batch experiments (19,27). In the present case of drying and recrystallizing cement, we employ an ACC

Table 1. Transformation kinetics during setting and hardening and final composition of several calcium carbonate cement pastes measured from in-situ time-lapse XRD scans

Sample	Total reaction time (h)	Final composition (%)		Time constant, τ (h) dissolution model	Final density, σ (g/cm^3)
		Calcite	Vaterite		
1:1wt%	10.00	98±2	2±1	12	1.11±0.01
1:2wt%	4.50	66±2	33±1	7	1.09±0.02
1:3wt%	3.00	59±2	40±1	5	1.08±0.02
1:2wt%+0.4v% OA	4.60	68±2	31±1	7	1.16±0.08

1:2wt%+0.8v% OA	4.90	70±2	29±1	7	1.20±0.05
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dissolution model which analyzes the evolution of the mass, m , of ACC. The theoretical interpretation coming out from this model is included on Figure 3 (solid line) along with the experimental data measured herein for the ACC phase from different cement pastes (ACC:V ratios). The obtained time constant values, τ , are $\tau_{\text{ACC:V } 1:1} = 12$ h, $\tau_{\text{ACC:V } 1:2} = 7$ h and $\tau_{\text{ACC:V } 1:3} = 5$ h. As for our previous study, there is a good agreement between the model and the data, which supports that the transformation of ACC to calcite within a cement paste system is limited by the dissolution of ACC, even under different setting conditions which do not allow a complete phase (re)crystallization of the initial reagents within the paste.

It is clear that the time constant $\tau \propto \frac{1}{K\Omega} \left(\frac{m_{v,0}}{N} \right)^{1/3}$ changes for each of the initial cement mixtures, increasing with the initial ACC content.

During the transformation, the liquid phase of the cement paste remains supersaturated with respect to calcite driving the precipitation of this phase. The resulting fine calcite crystallites begin to form an interconnected microstructure with particular pore structure and geometrical distribution. We suggest that subsequent crystal growth causes further hardening and strengthening of the cement matrix towards an overall mechanical resistance.

Figure 3. Normalized ACC mass evolution with time for three different pure CaCO_3 cement compositions (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 ACC:V wt.%) considering the supersaturation, Ω , proportional to the Gibbs free energy of the system ΔG . The solid line shows the outcome of the ACC dissolution model (Eq. SM.5).

3.2.2 The (lack of) effect of organic molecules

Figure 2 also shows the calculated molar fractions, X_i , of the three calcium carbonate polymorphs (ACC, vaterite and calcite) that coexist during the setting reaction for two CaCO_3 pastes with imbibed organic molecules. The 1:2 wt.%+0.4 v% OA specimen transforms linearly into calcite as without OA. After 4 h and 36 min, the reaction is completed and the set sample contains $68 \pm 2\%$ calcite and $31 \pm 1\%$ untransformed vaterite. For the 1:2 wt.%+0.8 v% OA paste, the reaction is over after 4 h and 54 min, leading to slightly greater final calcite content ($70 \pm 2\%$) and slightly lower untransformed vaterite amount ($29 \pm 1\%$). Moreover, XRD patterns remain nearly unchanged after 28 days as for the pure samples. Hence, a delayed effect of OA molecules among the CaCO_3 phase transformation mechanism is discarded.

The results show that the presence of OA molecules does not significantly modify the reaction rate nor the final phase composition when compared with their reference microstructure. Slightly longer reaction times lead to some extend higher calcite and consequently, somewhat lower vaterite amounts (Table 1). Moreover, the corresponding time constants, τ , obtained from the ACC dissolution model are the same as those obtained for the 1:2 wt.% composition ($\tau_{\text{ACC:V } 1:2+0.4 \text{ OA}} = 7 \text{ h}$ and $\tau_{\text{ACC:V } 1:2+0.8 \text{ OA}} = 7 \text{ h}$).

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3 Within the experimental uncertainty, the results show that there is no effect of OA on calcium carbonate
4 (re)crystallization. This signifies that OA does not impede calcite crystallization enough to become the rate
5 limiting process. We may also conclude that OA does not change the dissolution rate of ACC or vaterite. Similar
6 results were reported for carbonic anhydrase enzyme on lime mortars carbonation process (28). Thus, these
7 results are encouraging with respect to the inclusion of other biomolecules like proteins or antibiotics (within
8 similar concentrations) which may enhance other properties of the cements (like protein adhesion, bactericidal
9 effect, drug release, etc.) without modifying the crystallization pathway of the pastes since that is mainly
10 determined by the starting mixture design.
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20 3.3. CaCO_3 cements bioactivity

21 3.3.1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

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23 Figure 4 includes an example set of SEM micrographs obtained for the 1:1 wt% composition (A) before
24 immersion and after soaked in SBF for (D) 7 days, (E) 14 days and (F) 28 days (See SM.3 for (B) 1 day and (C)
25 3 days). The images obtained for all the other compositions are similar, including those containing organic
26 molecules. Therefore, we assume that their bioactive properties will be comparable as well in spite of their
27 differences in phase compositions.
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36 Figure 4A shows a microporous entangled network of small ($>5 \mu\text{m}$) rhombohedral calcite crystals. No changes
37 are observed in the cement surface (Figure SM.2B and C) until 7 days of immersion (Figure 4D) when the first
38 apatite-like crystals ($\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$) are detected. They are randomly distributed along the surface regardless of any
39 topographical features. One extra week of immersion (Figure 4E) results not only on double-sized ($\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$)
40 apatite-like crystals but also in a partly covered cement surface since those crystals start to merge and to form a
41 smooth layer. Upon immersion for 28 days (Figure 4F), almost the entire cement surface is covered by a
42 uniform apatite-like layer (identified by its crystal habit). Once again the crystal size has roughly doubled
43 indicating an approximately constant growth rate of $0.3 \mu\text{m}/\text{day}$. The appearance of well defined, isolated apatite
44 spheres indicates that there is a significant nucleation barrier to the apatite formation.
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Unfortunately, the final layer of apatite crystals was too thin to be correctly analyzed using energy dispersive x-rays (EDS), allowing a high contribution of Ca^{2+} counts coming from the bulk cement.

Figure 4. SEM micrographs obtained for the 1:1 wt% composition (A) before immersion in SBF and after soaked in SBF for, (D) 7 days, (E) 14 days and (F) 28 days. The arrows show the first apatite-like structures detected, (G) FTIR spectra and (H) XRD patterns of the CaCO_3 1:1 wt% composition after immersion in SBF for 0, 1, 3, 7, 14 and 28 days.

3.3.2. Fast transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

The FTIR spectra of the CaCO_3 1:1 wt% specimen immersed in SBF for 0, 1, 3, 7, 14 and 28 days are summarized in Figure 4G. The intense contribution at the CO_3^{2-} asymmetric bending bands located at 880 and 720 cm^{-1} is unsurprising since the cement is fully made of CaCO_3 (29,30). Moreover, FTIR spectroscopy provides further evidence for the formation of apatite-like structures and as such confirms the SEM observations. The intensity of the P-O bands, which are linked to apatite (PO_4^{3-} asymmetric stretching located at

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3 1010-1090 cm^{-1} (30,31) and 3 and 4 fold-rings PO_4^{3-} stretching modes located at 604 and 560 cm^{-1} , respectively
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5 (32)) increases with the immersion time.

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7 Overall, the results obtained for the other cement compositions are similar to the ones included here, in
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9 agreement with SEM observations.

10 11 12 3.3.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis

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14 For the CaCO_3 1:1 wt% composition, the XRD patterns (Figure 4H) obtained upon soaking in SBF for 0, 1, 3, 7,
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16 14 and 28 days, indicate that calcite is the final phase for this cement composition and that apatite-like crystals
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18 are of detectable size after 7 days of immersion. It is worth mentioning that the intensity recorded by XRD
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20 strongly depends on the degree of crystallinity of the scanned phases whereas vibrational spectroscopies (FTIR)
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22 are less sensitive to this parameter. This circumstance may explain why FTIR peaks (previous section) are more
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24 intense than the XDR peaks included on Figure 4H. However, looking closely there are two weak peaks (located
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26 at 32° and 33°) associated with apatite which increase in intensity with the immersion time (rectangular area in
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28 Figure 4H). Since no other intermediate crystalline phases are present, we can confirm that the reaction to form
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30 apatite-like structures was complete.

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33 As for the previous two characterization techniques, the results obtained for the other compositions are
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35 analogous, confirming that the bioactive properties do not depend on the cement composition.

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37 The crystalline apatite-like nucleation is taken as a proxy for the bioactive properties of the herein investigated
38
39 CaCO_3 cement compositions. In addition, the development of an apatite-like layer upon 28 days of immersion
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41 will enhance the cement bone-bonding aptitude since it plays a crucial role at the cement-bone interface (33).
42
43 Indeed, those results are in turn a proxy for the bonding extent at *in vivo* conditions.

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45
46 Furthermore, the results show that the particular compositions resulted from diverse ACC to vaterite ratios have
47
48 comparable bioactive properties, i.e. the kinetics for nucleation and growth of apatite-like crystals over their
49
50 surfaces are identical for all of them. During the initial stage of apatite growth, the mass of precipitate is
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52 nucleation-controlled whereas when the entire surface is covered after approximately a month, the growth is
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54 reaction-controlled. Perhaps, a common outer-most surface made of calcite crystals might explain these results.

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3 It is also noteworthy to mention that no changes in pH (7.40 ± 0.10) are observed in the SBF solutions after the
4 tests and consequently none of the cements are neither highly acidic nor basic compounds.

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7 In addition to the bone-bonding ability, it is generally accepted that micrometer surface roughness not only
8 facilitates the degradation of the materials leading to higher bioactivity rates (34,35) but enhance bone
9 formation, protein adsorption and cell proliferation (36,37). Given our SEM observations (Figure 4A-F), the
10 cements herein prepared are expected to be excellent bonding surfaces.

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13 The results also show that octanoic acid does not compromise the bioactive properties of the cement pastes
14 (within the concentration range studied). Consequently, it might contribute to enhance their overall performance.
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16 Further studies, however, will be necessary to confirm this approach extending the analysis to other molecules
17 with diverse carbon-chain lengths, concentrations and/or pH.
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20 21 22 23 24 25 *3.3.4. Effect of SBF immersion on uniaxial compressive strength (UCS)*

26
27 The UCS of all CaCO_3 cements herein studied after immersion in SBF for 0 (also referred as unsoaked samples),
28 1, 3, 7, 14 and 28 days is included in Figure 5. Among pure unsoaked samples, the 1:3 wt.% composition shows
29 the highest UCS, followed by the 1:2 wt.% and the 1:1 wt.%, respectively. This is consistent with our previous
30 study of CaCO_3 cement strength (18). As most cementitious materials, CaCO_3 cements are microporous and
31 their mechanical properties are highly influenced by their porosity. The apparent densities, ρ_a , calculated are
32 $1.11 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $1.09 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $1.08 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for the 1:1 wt.%, 1:2 wt.% and 1:3 wt.% set specimens,
33 respectively. Thus, by comparing these values, which show no statistical differences, with the density of calcite
34 (2.71 g/cm^3 (38)) a porosity of about 59-61% can be estimated for all of them. Even though each cement
35 composition has a particular distribution of CaCO_3 phases after the setting reaction, this approximation is fairly
36 accurate based on the similar density of the two most abundant phases within the set samples, i.e., calcite and
37 vaterite ($\rho_{\text{vaterite}} = 2.64 \text{ g/cm}^3$ (38)).
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41
42 On the other hand, the densities of the two compositions with imbibed organics, 1:2 wt.%+0.4 v% OA and 1:2
43 wt.%+0.8 v% OA, are $1.16 \pm 0.08 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $1.20 \pm 0.05 \text{ g/cm}^3$, respectively. Thus, despite of the lower weight to
44 volume ratio of octanoic acid (0.91 g/cm^3 (21)), the results show that its presence promote a more efficient
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packing of calcite and vaterite crystals during the recrystallization process, but a drop of about 30% in the compressive strength.

Theoretically, monodisperse rhombohedral calcite crystals can reach a high close-packing density, Φ_{CP} , as their lattice angle α approaches 90° (39). However, the cement samples here manufactured show low density values. Microstructural evidence (Figure 4A) indicates a random packing distribution which can be rationalized in the following way: once the newly-formed calcite crystals get in contact, they start to form clusters of coalesced or chained particles. Further crystal growth makes these clusters and single crystals to eventually merge and form a network with voids in between, containing CaCO_3 saturated water. With

Figure 5. Compressive strength of CaCO_3 cements before (unsoaked) and after immersion in SBF for 1, 3, 7, 14 and 28 days. Data are presented as mean values \pm standard deviation ($n=3$).

ongoing drying, the liquid phase continues supplying Ca^{2+} and CO_3^{2-} ions for crystal growth making the crystalline network denser until all water is consumed (or dried).

From this interpretation, if the newly formed calcite crystals get in contact since earlier stages of transformation, the overall bridging area within the calcite crystals will be larger, resulting on a better mechanical performance.

Thus, a larger total bridging area may be suggested for the 1:3 wt.% composition, since it displays the higher UCS, followed by the 1:2 wt.% and lastly the 1:1 wt.%. An analogous interpretation was found for tricalcium silicate (C_3S) pastes with the same porosity but diverse elastic modulus, E , and hardness, H , remarking the

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3 importance of the solid phases, their volumetric distribution and the joints strength in controlling the final
4 mechanical properties (40).

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7 Nevertheless, not only the total bridging area within the calcite network controls the UCS of CaCO_3 cements but
8 the degree of size polydispersity (PSD) within the initial solid reagents. With increasing PSD not only the
9 packing fraction of cement pastes increases exponentially but the overall mechanical properties, including
10 compression strength and elasticity (41). At this point, it is worth to remember that the average diameter of the
11 starting ACC and vaterite particles is one order of magnitude different. Consequently, it seems that a larger
12 starting amount of vaterite provides a higher degree of polydispersity (within the compositions here tested), since
13 the 1:3 wt.% shows the best mechanical properties.

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16 Compared with unsoaked references, the strength of all compositions drops considerably after the first day of
17 immersion in SBF although none of the hand specimens showed visual signs of degradation. Therefore, this
18 behavior must be a direct consequence of CaCO_3 dissolution. Similar results after 1 and 3 days of immersion
19 suggest that the SBF solution is already saturated on CaCO_3 within the first 24 hours (CaCO_3 solubility = 0.013
20 g/L at 25 °C (42)) stopping sample disintegration. However, the refreshment of the SBF solution every three
21 days allows the dissolution to proceed, increasing consequently the micro-porosity of the specimens and
22 reducing their nominal section area progressively whilst remaining optically invisible. Moreover, the strength
23 differences within all compositions vanish with increasing immersion time.

24
25
26 Greater density and the development of an apatite-like layer are features usually associated with a better
27 mechanical performance (43,44). However, the results show that the denser compositions, i.e., those containing
28 organic molecules, have a UCS similar to the average value measured for the 1:1 wt.% pastes after all soaking
29 periods. Thus, the presence of organics within the microstructure leads to denser but weaker grain networks,
30 probably due to the reduction of the overall joint area within calcite crystals.

31
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33 Comparing the UCS results with the bioactive rates obtained, the results show that the degradation kinetics of
34 the cements are greater than that of apatite-like nucleation and growth for all compositions and hence, the
35 influence of the apatite-like layer on the mechanical properties is not captured.

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3 To evaluate the potential use of bioactive CaCO_3 cements, their strength must be compared with that of human
4 bones. For instance, the average femur bone compressive strength is about 130 MPa (45), which is 23 times
5 higher than the largest value herein measured. From the previous interpretation, it seems that the packing density
6 of the cement samples, and hence the UCS, can be improved by letting the pastes to set under higher pressures.
7 However, further studies are still necessary to check this approach. Even though the overall compressive
8 strength of CaCO_3 cements remains poor, such mechanical properties would not be a handicap for secondary *in*
9 *vivo* applications like as bone-filling, especially in low mechanical stress locations since the release of calcium
10 and carbonate ions is believed to enhance the formation of new bone tissues (9).

20 **4. Conclusions**

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23 The cementing behavior of biomedical soluble calcium carbonate cements has been evaluated for different paste
24 designs, both in the absence and incorporating octanoic acid as a proxy for organic molecules. Time-revolved
25 *in-situ* x-ray diffraction results showed that the (re)crystallization kinetics depend on the reagent concentration,
26 producing typical microstructures. All starting compositions lead to microporous samples composed of >59%
27 calcite being the transformation from ACC and vaterite to calcite controlled by the dissolution of ACC. A higher
28 initial vaterite concentration has the dual effect of boosting the reaction rate, as well as an early termination.

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31 The inclusion of organic molecules within the cement microstructures, however, does not generate specific
32 behavior within the concentration range studied, opening the possibility to extend the study to other kind of
33 biomolecules like proteins or antibiotics.

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36 The bioactive properties of CaCO_3 cements have been confirmed by apatite-like nucleation after 7 days of
37 immersion in simulated body fluid and the development of a bone-like layer beyond that point, even for those
38 compositions with imbibed organics. This coating is expected to enhance the bone bonding aptitude of these
39 cements. Once implanted, CaCO_3 cements will start dissolving and consequently reducing their overall
40 mechanical properties, but releasing calcium and carbonate ions which will enhance the formation of new bone
41 tissues. Even though the compressive strength of all CaCO_3 cements remained poor, their high solubility, fast
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3 setting kinetics and bioactive properties still makes them suitable candidates for *in vivo* applications such as
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5 bone filler, especially in low mechanical stress locations.
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9

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Supplementary material

SM.1. Mole fraction evolution from XRD

XRD patterns were recorded every 5 min for a maximum of 14 hours. The apparent mole fraction evolution with time of vaterite, X_V' , and calcite, X_C' , phases ($X_V' + X_C' = 1$) were determined using the software DiffraC.Suite TOPAS (Bruker AXS, USA). Since vaterite and ACC were the starting reagents, the initial ACC molar fraction, $X_{ACC}(t_0)$, could be calculated from the starting vaterite molar fraction, $X_V'(t_0)$, as:

$$X_{ACC}(t_0) = 1 - X_V'(t_0) \quad (\text{SM.1})$$

To include the evolution of the ACC phase within the previous calculations, calcite mole fraction, X_C , was calculated considering that $X_C + X_V + X_{ACC} = 1$ in the following way:

$$X_C = (X_C'(t) - X_C'(t_0)) \cdot \frac{X_C'(t_f)}{X_C'(t_f) - X_C'(t_0)} \quad (\text{SM.2})$$

SM.2. Crystal dissolution rate model

In order to model the behaviour, we follow (18) and describe the crystal dissolution rate, r , which can be expressed as:

$$r = -K \cdot A \cdot e^{\frac{-E_a}{RT}} \cdot f(\Delta G) \quad (\text{SM.3})$$

where K is the dissolution rate constant ($\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$), A is the reactive surface area of the dissolving phase, E_a is the apparent activation energy of the overall reaction, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature and $f(\Delta G)$ introduces the dependence of the overall dissolution rate on the undersaturation state of the system expressed as a function, f , of the Gibbs free-energy change for the dissolution reaction, ΔG .

In our previous study (18) we found that for wet CaCO_3 cements the transformation mechanism was limited by the dissolution of vaterite and not by the available surface area of calcite as has been reported for batch experiments (19,27). In the present case of drying and recrystallizing cement, we employ an ACC dissolution

model which analyzes the evolution of the mass, m , of ACC. Figure SM.1. includes the normalized mass evolution recorded for ACC particles within three different pure CaCO_3 cement compositions (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 ACC:V wt.%) and two with imbibed organic molecules (1:2+0.4 v.% OA and 1:2+0.8 v.% OA). They

Figure SM.1. Normalized ACC mass evolution with time for three different pure CaCO_3 cement compositions (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 ACC:V wt.%) and two with imbibed organic molecules (1:2+0.4 v.% OA and 1:2+0.8 v.% OA) showing the data collapse.

univocally show a data collapse.

Moreover, we know that the area, A , of the dissolving ACC particles is proportional to $2/3$ of their mass: $A \propto m_{ACC}^{2/3}$, and making use of Eq. SM.3, the evolution of the mass can be described by the following equation:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -\varphi \cdot m_{ACC}^{2/3} \quad (\text{SM.4})$$

where φ is a constant term that includes the contribution of the dissolution rate constant, K , and the supersaturation, $\Omega = \Delta G/RT$, of the system. Thus, it could be expressed as $\varphi = K \left(\frac{\Delta G}{RT} \right)^n$. By integrating Eq. SM.4 from the initial, $m_{ACC,0}$, to the final, m_{ACC} , ACC mass for the entire duration of the transformation, t , the following expression is obtained:

$$\frac{m_{ACC}}{m_{ACC,0}} = \left(1 - \frac{t}{\tau}\right)^3 \quad (\text{SM.5})$$

where τ represents the time constant of the transformation and it is defined as $\tau = 3m_{ACC,0}^{1/3}(RT/\Delta G)^n/K$.

This theoretical interpretation is included on **Error! Reference source not found.** (solid line) along with the experimental data measured herein for the ACC phase from different cement pastes (ACC:V ratios).

SM.3. CaCO_3 cements bioactivity. SEM analysis

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5 **Figure SM.2.** SEM micrographs obtained for the 1:1 wt% composition (A) before immersion in SBF and after
6 soaked in SBF for (B) 1 day, (C) 3 days, (D) 7 days, (E) 14 days and (F) 28 days.
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